

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITION AND TECHNOLOGY OF FACE CREAM**Rahmatjonova L.B.¹****Rizaeva N.M.²**

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Relevance: This work presents a developed natural face cream based on coconut oil and talc, which has moisturizing, softening, and mating properties. Coconut oil, due to its high content of fatty acids and antioxidants, has a nutritional and protective effect on the skin, contributing to the restoration of its lipid balance and increased elasticity. Talc, in turn, provides a mating effect by absorbing excess sebum, giving the skin smoothness and velvety texture. Studies have been conducted on the physical and chemical properties of the cream, its stability, and organoleptic tests. The results showed the high effectiveness of the developed product when used daily, which confirms the prospects for its use in the cosmetics industry.

Research objective: Cream with mineral composition is a safer and physiologically compatible option, especially for people with sensitive and problematic skin. Unlike creams with synthetic composition, natural remedies have a mild effect on the skin and a low risk of allergic reactions due to their natural origin. The purpose of the work is to develop the composition and technology of face cream with a natural composition (based on coconut oil and talc).

Materials and methods: Mineral creams contain natural inorganic components and vegetable oils that provide a gentle and physiologically compatible effect on the skin. In the first stage, coconut oil - a natural vegetable oil obtained from the flesh of mature coconuts - was chosen as the base for the cream. It is an inert component that does not penetrate deep into the skin and also possesses a number of valuable pharmacological properties. Coconut oil is composed of 90-95% saturated fatty acids, the main of which is lauric acid, which has pronounced antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. The composition also includes myristic, caprylic, capric, and palmitic acids, which contribute to skin nourishment and protection. The presence of vitamin E acts as an antioxidant, slowing down the aging process. Additionally, coconut oil forms a thin protective film on the skin surface that prevents moisture loss. Talc - a natural mineral, chemically represented as magnesium hydrosilicate - was chosen as the second main component. In cosmetic formulations, talc performs several important functions: it provides a pronounced mattifying effect due to the absorption of skin oil, gives the product a velvety texture, and promotes a more even distribution across the skin. To enhance the functional properties of the cream, auxiliary components were added to the composition: starch, glycerin, and water, which provide additional moisturizing, improvement of texture, and sensory characteristics. As a thickener, the base uses methylcellulose - a water-soluble polysaccharide of plant origin, which gives the cream the necessary viscosity, prevents phase separation, improves the homogeneity of the texture, and helps retain moisture on the skin.

Results: The quality indicators of the cream - such as appearance, homogeneity, pH, mass fraction of water and volatile substances, colloidal and thermal stability - were assessed according to the methods described in the scientific literature. Based on the conducted research, it was established that natural face cream based on coconut oil and talc has high efficacy and safety. Methylcellulose as a base provides ease of application, sorbic acid as a preservative ensures long-term storage of the prepared face cream. The composition and technology for making cream based on natural minerals have been developed and experimentally confirmed.

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Conclusions: Thus, the results of the conducted experiments made it possible to scientifically substantiate the composition and technology for obtaining a natural multicomponent face cream intended for daily skincare of all types.